

رسالة المكتبة

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الببليوغرافي .

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تصنيف كتب الجغرافيا في المكتبات: دراسة نقدية لنظام التصنيف البيبليوغرافي

Classification of Geography Books in Libraries: A Critique of the Bibliographic Classification (BC)

By
*Dr. Mohamed Salah Eldin Mudawi*¹

مستخلص

رغم التطور الكبير في علم "الجغرافيا"، و اكتسابه لمكانة متميزة بين العلوم، يأتي تصنيف هذا العلم ضمن فروع علوم أخرى في المكتبات التي تستخدم نظام التصنيف البيبليوغرافي، مثل الجيولوجيا والاقتصاد والعلوم السياسية والاجتماع والتاريخ، مما يشتت كتب العلوم الجغرافية في مواقع مختلفة وقد أدى ذلك في نهاية الأمر إلى توزيع و تشتيت كتب العلوم الجغرافية في مواقع مختلفة داخل المكتبة الواحدة، ويسبب إرباكا للمستفيدين وهذا يتعارض مع أهم أهداف التصنيف و هي تسهيل الوصول إلى المواد المكتبية بترتيبها وفقاً لنظام منطقي و سهل. تم تطبيق الدراسة على مكتبة جامعة الخرطوم لإظهار الفكرة الرئيسية للمقال، ويوصي الكاتب بضرورة تصنيف بديل وموحد يمكن من تنظيم الموضوع ككل في موقع واحد

Abstract

Despite various phases of development that geography has experienced, and lot of merits among the other subjects geography books in libraries adopting Bibliographic classification (BC) are classified under subjects other than geography, e.g. e.g. geology, economics, political sciences, social sciences and history. Geography books in this way are located in different places inside the library, which would be confusing for users. Taking Khartoum University Library as an example, the author recommends necessity of providing alternative class for geography books, to enable librarians locate the entire subject in one place.

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1. Introduction:

In the field of Information and Library studies, there are some vital tools, which are used in the process of organization of knowledge. One of these key tools is the *Classification Scheme*. A library classification scheme is the system designed to arrange the physical items of the library collection. So any library arranges its stock according to the Classification Scheme in use in that library. The classification scheme is used to help in classifying the library stock by subjects. The objective of classification is to get the book to the reader or the reader to the book in the quickest possible time (Harrison and Beenham, 1985:47).

For any classification scheme to be recognized, a logical arrangement of subjects is needed, accompanied by a system of symbols, known as *notation*, used to represent the classes in the classification scheme.

In the field of Information and Library Sciences, there are many classification Schemes. The most prominent ones are the *Library of Congress (LC)*; *Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC)*; *the Bibliographic Classification (BC)*; and others. Each scheme provides a coherent and comprehensive system, with the systems of sciences and education standards.

2. Bibliographic Classification Scheme (BC):

The Bibliographic Classification Scheme (BC) is a fully developed system that specifies categories down to the finest gradations, it provides the means to relate the categories and specify in the notation all of the aspects and facets of a work (Dewey, 1989: Li). This scheme is one of the most extensive classification schemes; it is applicable not merely to books on shelves of libraries, but to different bibliographic services. The bibliographic Classification scheme (BC) was developed by Henry Evelyn Bliss (1870-1955), an American Librarian. He conceived the scheme as long as 1908, but

it was not until 1953 that, a condensed version of it was published, and (1904-53) that the full edition appeared in print.

The BC scheme has been widely praised mainly because of its very logical arrangement. It is the most scholarly of all the classification schemes. The provision for its revision has not been compared with the other Schemes. So it has become outdated (Harrison and Beenham, 1985: 59).

It has been estimated that, about 90 libraries all over the world used this Scheme. The users are mainly academic, learned, government, and special libraries (Harrison and Beenham, 1985: 59).

3. Bibliographic Classification Scheme and Geography:

BC scheme deals mainly with the human knowledge and its main objective is to find a practical answer to the question how this Knowledge can be arranged, controlled and accessible. Thus the Scheme tries to classify and arrange this knowledge in a logical sequence. It divides this knowledge into its major subsets i.e. subjects e.g. Physics, Botany, History, Philosophy, Geography....etc.

The Scheme has developed certain sequences for the subjects to be classified, and then, according to this classification, to be shelved inside the libraries. Among these subjects, definitely, is geography. For details about the Bibliographic Classification see Figure (1).

While treating the subject matter of Geography, the BC scheme has made some faults in determining where and what geography position is. So this article is an attempt to examine how geography has been treated, classified and shelved inside the libraries, according to the BC Scheme, taking Khartoum University Library, which adopted BC Scheme, as an example.

Figure (1)

Outlines of Bibliographic Classification

Class	Subject
2/9	Generalia, Phenomena, Knowledge, Information science & technology
A/AL	Philosophy & Logic. 1991
AM/AX	Mathematics, Probability, Statistics. 1993
AY-B	General science, Physics. 1999
C	Chemistry, Chemical Engineering. 2002
D	Space & Earth sciences
	Astronomy
	Geology
	Geography
E/GQ	Biological sciences
E	Biology
	Biochemistry
	Genetics
	Virology
F	Botany
G	Zoology
GR	Agriculture
GU	Veterinary science
GY	Applied Ecology, Human environment
H	Physical Anthropology, Human biology, Health sciences.
I	Psychology & Psychiatry. 1978
J	Education. Rev. ed. 1990
K	Society (includes Social Sciences, sociology, & social Anthropology)
L/O	History, (includes Archaeology, biography and travel)
P	Religion, Occult, Morals and ethics.
Q	Social welfare & Criminology.
R	Politics & Public administration.
S	Law. 1996
T	Economics & Management of economic enterprises. 1987
U/V	Technology, Engineering. 2001
W	Recreation, Arts, Music
X/Y	Language, Literature

Source: Compiled by the author from: Bliss, Henry Evelyn (1953).

3.1 False Dichotomy:

One of major defects in the BC Scheme when treating geography is that, it considers geography as a dichotomous subject, i.e. geography has been dealt with as two distinct parts. e.g. *the human geography* on one hand and *physical geography* on the other hand. The major problem here is that, whenever geography is classified as a two-fold subject, this means that, geography will automatically be located and shelved in different places inside the library. In fact, the concept of dichotomous subject contradicts the scope and spirit of modern geography, as it has been perceived by geographers of today.

Throughout the history of the subject, since Humboldt and Ritter (1769-1859) up to the recent generation, the majority of geographers believe that both human and physical geography should be expressed together as a single subject. A wealth of literature was written to support this argument. For instance both Humboldt and Ritter were engrossed in the coherent relations of the physical and biological phenomena of the earth's surface, and both were clearly aware that human phenomena showed correlation with physical condition, and as an integral and harmonious part of the complete picture (Woodridge and East, 1966: 20). It is obvious that, the major aim of his concept of "one geography" was to consider natural (including human, culture, behavior and activities) phenomena in a natural perspective, within the context of causal relations and interaction between such physical and human environment.

Those pioneer geographers were convinced that, the earth and its inhabitants stand in the closest mutual relations, and there is a universal agreement, among geographers that geographical work focuses on the study of this relationship (Woodridge and East, 1966:23).

On the other hand recent geographers still believe that geography occupies a puzzling position within the organization of knowledge. Johnston (1981) stated “the majority of the recent geographers have thought the distinction between natural and man – made phenomena unhelpful since it obscured some of the essential characteristics of geographical study, and therefore undermined its long – term rationale as a university discipline”.

It is evident that geography concerns man and land. The field can therefore be approached from the side of either land or man or both. But there is a danger of false dichotomy here, as expressed by Woodridge (1966), “a division of the subject into “*physical geography*” and “*human geography*” such a cleavage is wholly antithetic to geography”.

So it is clear and obvious that, geographers do believe that their subject should be dealt with as one concrete and intgral body.

While treating the position of geography among the other subjects, the Bibliographic Classification contradicts this notion. The introductory chapter of the Bibliographic Classification stated “this system is mainly consistent with the systems of science and education established in the consensus of scientists and educators and embodied in their institutions, curricula and program “Bliss, 1953:21).

It seems that this is one of the core principles of the Bibliographic Classification scheme, but this seems no longer valid when the BC deals with geography. It is evident that nearly all of geographers and professionals believe in integrity rather than dichotomy.

Bliss (1953) has admitted that he faced many difficulties when he dealt with geography, he states, “one of our major problems has been geography”.

Bliss stated more about geography "it has so many relations that it can not feasibly be localized or unified as some of its professor's desire "(vol.111, p.29). This has confused Bliss and in his attempt to overcome this difficulty, he ignores one of his "golden *principles*" the scientists' consensus.

As Bliss has decided to divide the subject into parts, geography is composite of wide range of studies related on one hand to physiographic geology, and on the other hand to biological, ethnical, social and economic studies. Human geography (anthropography) should be collocated with ethnography and Socio political history. The physical geography (physiography) should be collocated with physiographic geology. (Bliss, 1953,vol-1-11, part II: DQ).

From what Bliss has stated in his scheme it is obvious that the BC had developed a false dichotomy which denies one of geography's distinctive features and characteristics among other subjects, as geographers believe that geography should take the responsibility of bridging the gap between the physical and human phenomena and study the causal relations between them.

3.2 Misplacing of Geography Books:

It has been agreed that, one of the major objectives of the library classification scheme is to get the book to the reader or the reader to the book. This can actually be achieved by classifying and shelving books on the same subject together in one location, and books on related subjects alongside.

If this happens, it will save a lot of time for the library user. When a library user knows the location of subject he/she interested in, just by browsing the location, the user would be able to choose the book (s) he wants. Sometimes the process of browsing the shelves may lead to some unexpected titles, of

great value to the user, But one can imagine how the users selection of books, would be difficult if books of one subject e.g. geography, are classified and then shelved in different physical locations, in a very huge library.

Some body may raise the point that, the library searching tools like catalogues, may help solving this problem. Actually it is evident that, in most cases library users are used to ask broadly “where can I find books on geography? Moreover, in non-automated libraries, the use of catalogues is a time and effort-consuming work, besides it needs some sort of training.

One of the major defects of the Bibliographic Classification scheme when dealing with geography is that, it scatters books on geography into different locations in the library. Some of the geography books are classified and shelved with geology, some with economics, and some with anthropology and some with agriculture.

One of best examples of scattering and misplacing of geography books in a library classified by BC scheme, is the case of Khartoum University Library. This Library occupies almost 6800sq. meters, with a collection of more that 800,000 volumes. It occupies a huge historic building with two floors. Until 1995 this library used to classify its collection by the Bibliographic Classification scheme. Although the scheme is changed now into Dewey Decimal Classification DDC, the library stocks are still shelved according to the BC, as the process of *reclassification* of the library stock is a very huge task, which needs long time to be accomplished.

Khartoum University Library provides an outstanding example for the geography books classified by the BC and how they have been scattered to a confusing extent. Figure (2), which has been extracted form the BC's index, provides an illustrative example for how books of geography are classified

and where they can be shelved in a library according to the BC Scheme. While Figure (3) shows the distribution of books by subjects in the Khartoum University Library as per the Bibliographic Classification.

Together Figure (2) and Figure (3), could illustrate how geography books are distributed and Scattered in different physical locations under different subjects. This has created a real confusion to geography students and other users of geography books.

3.3 Geography Subordination:

Geography as a science is not new, but it is an old one, “our geographic plant, truly plant, is very old, not young” (Finch, 1939: 3). In its historical development, geography occupies a logical defensible position among the sciences as one of the chronological studies, which attempt to consider not particular kinds of Objects and objects in reality, but actual sections of reality, which attempt to analyze and synthesize not processes of phenomena as related in sections of reality. (Harshorne: 1939).

During its history, geography has witnessed several developments, but during the 1950's geography had undergone a radical transformation of spirit and scope best described as “*quantitative revolution*” the ideas of this revolution are now conventional. The development of theoretical model building of geography on a solid scientific basis is likely to be the major consequence of this revolution (Burton, 1968: 18). Thus geography has developed its own theories, methodologies and has ended up with huge literature. All these factors have qualified geography to be considered as a literary warrant science.

Figure (2)

The Class Mark of Different Branches of Geography According To the Bibliographic Classification Scheme. *

Branch	Class Mark	Branch	Class Mark
Anthropogeography	KT	Mathematical Geog.	DQA
Atlases	11; DQ5; LIZ	Measures in Geog.	DQE
Biogeography	EM; ET	Medical Geog.	HPW; HQZ
Climatology	DSR; DSS; ELF	Physical Geog.	DR
Commercial Geog.	TMO	Political Geog.	L3
Economic Geog.	T4	Population Geog.	KAS;KTP; TBH
Gazettes	11; L14	Regional Geog.	DT
Geomorphology	DK	Social Geog.	KT;KAT
Historical Geog.	L3	Societies for Geog.	DQ53; L353
History of Geog.	L33; DQ3	Soil Geog.	FF; KT; UA
Human Geog.	KT	Teaching for Geog.	DQ
Hydrology	DRH	Thoughts of Geog.	DQ
Industrial Geog.	TDB	Transport Geog.	TN
Maps & charts	DQA	Zoogeography	GH

SOURCE:

Compiled by the author from: **Bliss, Henry Evelyn** (1953). Vol. IV; p. 156

* To identify location of each class mark in the library, please see Figure (3).

Figure (3)

**Distribution of Books by Subjects According to BC
Khartoum University Library (sketched with no scale)**

O Pacific Hist.	Philos. A	Religion. A	Math. A	Physics B	Chemistry C	Geology D	Biology			
N African Hist.						E				
P Asian Hist.	L History	M	K Anthrop.	G Zoology		F Botany				
Arabic lang. Collections	 First Floor Plan									
Internet Laboratories	Key: <table border="1" style="margin-left: auto; margin-right: auto;"> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">T</td> <td>Boxed letters indicate location of Geography books as per BC.</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;">A</td> <td>Non boxed letters indicate books for other subjects.</td> </tr> </table>							T	Boxed letters indicate location of Geography books as per BC.	A
T	Boxed letters indicate location of Geography books as per BC.									
A	Non boxed letters indicate books for other subjects.									

Economics T	Political Sc. R	Psychology I	J Education
Economics T	R Political Sc.	Anthropology K	
European Languages	Ground Floor Plan		Periodical Section
Tighani Al- Mahi Library			

Despite this history and development, the Bibliographic Classification Scheme tends to deny geography its acceptable position among Sciences especially in the recent situation and time.

The BC used to deal with geography as a subordinate subject to other subjects but never as an independent subject. The BC scatters the Branches of geography each one, to the related subjects, this is one thing which denies geography its unique unity and integration e.g. general geography and physical or physiographical and regional geography are classified under the earth sciences (Class-D), and anthropogeography or human geography is closely related to ethnography as well as to socio-economic history, so they are classified under the anthropology (class K), the economic geography is classified under the economics (class T), and political geography, is classified under the social and political history (Class-L).

By doing this, it seems that, the BC scheme does not have a clear definition and apprehension of geography as a discipline of its own right, and geography has been looked upon as just a synopsis of other sciences. i.e. geography drew its materials from a variety of sciences and disciplines.

It is obvious that geography is not an isolated subject, rather it has some relations and intersections with the other subjects and discipline, actually there is no isolated discipline, as all disciplines have got, by way or another, some relations and intersections with each other.

Trying to place geography among the human knowledge Singh and Singh (1977) suggested that "if the human Knowledge is divided into four major themes or subsets within a single set, they will include: geo-sciences, bio-sciences, physical sciences, and humanities. So one can certainly state that,

the geographic approaches are lying in all the four sets at different level of emphasis and form. So the intersecting paradigms show the core position of geography among other sciences".

The viewpoint of the Bibliographic Classification about geography as a synoptic of sciences was totally refused by geographers. This argument assumes that synoptic sciences are redundant i.e. they do not create new and valuable ideas. According to Finch (1939) "geographers believe that every science involves an interrelation of facts from other sources, but from them each makes its own explanation".

When the Bibliographic Classification scheme treats geography as a redundant, it fails to consider that geography has got some intersection with other subjects, and has drawn some facts from these sciences, but geography is not agglomeration of pieces of systematic sciences rather it integrates these fact to its distinctive geographic point of view.

In the same regard Harshorne (1939) believes that "although some geography facts have been drawn from other subjects, but they have been adopted for the geography's own specific ends, and developed by geography's distinctive techniques and approaches".

Having this in mind, it will be quite unsatisfactory to classify a book entitled: *An Introduction to physical geography*, under earth sciences (class D), or a book entitled: *Basics of Economic geography*, under economics (Class T) or a book entitled: *political Geography: a study on politics and environment*, under socio-political history (class L).

Although these books have shared some characteristics of the subjects under which they have been classified, the exact location for them should remain under a separate class labeled for geography and not for any other subject. All those books were written mainly by geographers, and not by geologists,

economists, or even historians. The target groups of beneficiaries for these books are geographers and geography students, in the first place.

Furthermore, these books are based upon the techniques and theories, which were adopted and developed mainly by geographers.

It is true that, these books may be valuable for non-geographers who are working for understanding different phenomena, in fields that intersecting with geography. But ultimately these titles should be dealt with as geography books and not any other subjects.

Actually the classification of geography books under other subjects gives one the feeling that geography has come into existence not to contribute to human knowledge by its own methodologies, techniques, theories and literature. Rather one may feel it has come just as a complementary subject, and not to build itself as a recognized discipline.

4. Conclusion:

Despite the various phases of development that geography has experienced, geography books are classified and shelved in libraries in a confusing arrangement, for library users in general and geography students in particular. Actually this arrangement is responsible for minimizing the utilization of geography books inside these libraries. In fact this illogical arrangement of geography books contradicts one of the major golden rules in librarianship: "*Books for use*". From a personal experience, while using the library as an undergraduate geography student, it was my believe that, a large proportion of geography student is extremely confused by such classification and arrangement for geography books. For geographers, geography is considered as a fully developed, articulated and integrated subject. But for non-geographers, among them, definitely, are librarians, it is

still a controversial issue. So one of the urgently needed solutions for the classification of geography books in the Bibliographic Classification is to provide an alternative unitary class for geography books, which will enable the libraries to locate the entire subject in one place.

For the non-geographers to perceive the full image of geography as perceived by geographers, professional geographers are urgently requested to exert some serious efforts, to build a solid theoretical framework, to illustrate where geography actually stands among the set of sciences.

* * * * *

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